

Application of Eco-Friendly and Enzyme Based Stain Removers in Textiles

Harinder Pal*, Sagarika Pal & Nisha Jangra

Dept. of Fashion Technology, Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya, Khanpur Kalan, Sonipat,
HR

Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate the environmental impact of chemical stain removers, detergents, and review critically enzyme-based stain removers as an alternative to replace synthetic surfactants in textile industry. It also highlights some of the chemically based stain removers, which are eco-friendly and could be used as stain removers. Literature review reveals that the usage of enzyme-based products in industrial and household chores is growing day by day. Previous Research findings also indicate that enzyme-based products exhibit high efficacy in eliminating stubborn stains, while maintaining fabric integrity, which contributes to their popularity among environmental conscious consumers. Moreover, the adoption of these products can result in reduced water and energy consumption during laundry, leading to further environmental benefits. There are six kind of enzyme that are currently used in various industry; Oxidoreducers, Transferases, Hydrolysers, Lyases, Isomerizers, and Ligases. In these, hydrolysers enzymes like proteases, lipases, amylases, and cellulases are popularly used in washing industry. The paper discusses their mechanisms of action on stains and how it increases the rate of reaction. Overall, this review highlights the environmentally responsible choice of enzyme-based detergents and stain removers over conventional chemical-based alternatives. By replacing synthetic surfactants in the textile industry and promoting the utilization of eco-friendly stain removers, this study advocates for sustainable practices in cleaning and laundry, offering significant potential for reducing the environmental impacts associated with these processes.

Keywords: Detergent, Environment, Enzyme, Mechanism, Surfactant, Stain Remover

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. Harinder Pal,
Assistant Professor,
Department of Fashion Technology,
Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya,
Khanpur Kalan, Sonipat, Haryana-131 305
E-mail: harinderarora@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Environmental contamination caused by industrial activities is increasing day by day which have also increased the environmental conscious awareness among consumers. Washing products, such as laundry detergent, soap, and stain remover, can have both environmental and human health impacts which may be a cause of concern among users. These products contain a variety of chemicals that can be harmful to aquatic life, contribute to air pollution, and potentially cause health issues in humans. Aquatic life is frequently affected when detergents are dumped into natural water [1, 2]. Researchers have experimentally measured the harmful impacts of these chemicals and tried to find the eco-friendly solutions for the same. These detergents and stain removers contain such things as builders, surfactants, functional substances, dye transfer inhibitors, fragrance, phosphates etc. The harmful effects of phosphates as builders and surfactants as surface-active agents caused the most significant problem faced by the environment due to detergent industry. Phosphorus is a non-toxic chemical that acts as a plant nutrient [3, 4, 5]. Phosphates are primarily used in detergents to ensure efficient cleaning in hard water. According to the United States Environmental Protection Agency's national aquatic resource surveys, phosphorus is described as a "limiting nutrient," and the permissible limit of phosphate in detergent is 0.5%. Studies show that due to the excess use of this product, the phosphate level in soil, water bodies, rivers, underground water, etc. may increase [6]. Phosphorus can cause issues with water quality, including eutrophication and damaging algal development, when it is present in excess. According to David W. Litke [7] excessive use of phosphorus in

fertilizer, manure, and laundry detergents is harmful and was prohibited in 1994. European Union introduced regulations and ban phosphates in domestic products in 2013 in a phased manner.

Synthetic surfactants are found to cause continuous foaming in rivers, sewage treatment plants, and around drainage discharges. Synthetic surfactants are very toxic and have low biodegradability. Bio-surfactants are possible replacements for synthetic surfactants as these cause harmful impact on the environment, including destruction of marine microbial communities, detriment to fish and other aquatic life, decreased capacity of photochemical power production in plants, and interference with wastewater treatment procedures. There is an immediate need for replacements of these harmful surfactants on a global scale, which are being used at the scale of 15 million metric tons per year, with 60% of those surfactants ending up in the aquatic system [8]. Wastewater that produced by domestic and industrial processes, such as washing clothes, yarn, fabric, and so on, is known as grey water. There is 50–80% of grey water produced by domestic activities, where the amount of laundry grey water represents 33%. This raw grey water is very harmful for soil. Grey water contains high quantities of sodium (Na) which promotes deterioration of soil condition and mobility. It also increases the pH level, which causes a high concentration of alkaline detergents when unclean grey water is used to fertilize land. Due to lack of awareness in implementing stringent rules and regulations in developing countries, they are found to discharge the grey water into the soil, which is not acceptable because it introduces pollutants like organic micro pollutants, chemical agents, and pathogens into fresh water and soil which affects humans via food chain [9].

In terms of human health, different cleaning substances represent different kinds of health risks. Some are linked to cancer's chronic or long-term impacts, while other poses acute or instant threats, including skin or breathing problems, watery eyes, and even chemical burns. People who have asthma, lung, or heart related problems should avoid using such chemical agents like ammonia and chlorine bleach because of their constituents has high acute toxicity. Many cleaners, including laundry detergents and fabric softeners, contain fragrances that can have immediate side effects on people such as hypertension, red eyes, sniffing, and lung discomfort. Cleaning products also pose a risk to the environment since many of them contain petroleum-based substances, which increase our reliance on foreign oil resources and contribute to the decline of non-renewable fuels [10].

To reduce the environmental and human health impacts of washing products, it's important to choose products that are environment friendly.

2. Stain and Stain Remover

A stain is the result of a chemical interaction between the staining substance and the fabric or finish. Because the chemical nature of every stain and substance is different, so therefore there is no particular solution or procedure for eliminating all stains. Stain remover refers to a product or chemical used to remove stains from clothing, fabric, or other washable materials. These products are designed to break down and remove specific types of stains, such as food, oil, ink, grass, and blood. Stain removers are available in various forms, such as liquids, powders, or sprays, and can be applied directly to the stain before washing or added to the washing machine along with the detergent. The effectiveness of a laundry stain remover may depend on the type of stain, the fabric, and the severity of the stain, among other factors [3,11].

2.1 Type and Mechanisms of stain remover

Since there is no particular solution or procedure for eliminating all stains, hence there exists several kinds of stain removers in market or at home in the form of natural and chemical based ingredients. Different stain removers works on different mechanism using different methods. Natural stain removers are eco-friendly and safe for humans as well as for animals. In this paper, a review on the different stain remover has been done and discusses different kinds of stain removers [3].

2.1.1 Eco Friendly Stain Removers

There are several kinds of are eco-friendly and natural stain-removers that can be used for removing stain from fabric, the briefing of which is mentioned below:

Baking Soda: Baking soda is a non-toxic and versatile cleaner. It has an abrasive texture that helps to loosen dirt and stains from fabrics. Baking soda also acts as a natural deodorizer, which helps to eliminate odors from clothes.

Vinegar: Vinegar is a cleaning agent that helps to remove stains, odors, and dirt from clothes. It has acetic acid, which is effective at breaking down dirt and grime. Vinegar is also an eco-friendly fabric softener, which helps to keep clothes soft and fluffy.

Lemon Juice: Lemon juice is a natural bleaching agent that helps to remove stains and brighten clothes. It is effective on mildew, rust, and other stubborn stains. Lemon juice also acts as a natural fabric softener [4, 11].

Hydrogen Peroxide: Hydrogen peroxide is a bleaching agent that helps to remove stains and brighten clothes. It is effective on blood, grass, and other stubborn stains. Hydrogen peroxide also acts as a disinfectant, which helps to kill germs and bacteria [14].

Cornstarch: Cornstarch is a natural and effective stain remover for greasy and oily stains. It works by absorbing the oils and grease from the fabric, making it easier to wash the stain away. To use cornstarch as a fabric stain remover, sprinkle a small amount of cornstarch onto the greasy or oily stain and let it be there for a few minutes [1].

These agents can be used in combination with each other or with traditional laundry detergents to provide effective cleaning results. It is important to test each natural agent on a small area of fabric before using it on the entire garment to prevent any damage or discoloration.

2.1.2 Chemical Detergents and Stain Remover

Stain remover and detergent are composed of various chemicals and solvents. These cleaning solutions are a mixture of builders, surface-active agents (surfactants), additives, and fillers [5]. Surfactant is a surface-active agent that aids in the reduction of surface tension and the enhancement of cleaning performance. Surfactants act as detergents, wetting agents, emulsifiers, foaming agents, and dispersants [15]. Builder is used as a softener to remove the heavy metals in the water. Additives enhance the washing power. Many components are added to the additives, like bleach, fragrance, optical brightener; stain remover, etc. [3, 2].

2.1.2.1 Mechanisms of Surfactant for Removing Stain

Detergent containing surfactants with emulsifying properties decreases its surface tension and increases the spreading and soaking capabilities of the water. Surfactants also aid in the uniform penetration of the dye into the fabric during textile dyeing [2].

The heads of the surfactant molecules are hydrophilic in nature and the tails are hydrophobic. During laundry washing, the hydrophobic end of the surfactant is attached to the dirt particles on the fabric as shown in fig 1. When a sufficient amount of surfactant is added to the water, it creates micelles around the dirt. When micelles attach to dirt, their hydrophilic heads are drawn to water, and the fabric gets cleaned. Since only surfactant is not sufficient to clean and remove odors from laundry after washing so other components are also used along with it [16].

Figure 1: The function of a surfactant

Source: <https://www.novozymes.com/en/campaigns/towards-100-biological-detergents>

2.1.3 Enzymes Based Stain Remover

Enzyme is a biodegradable compound that helps to catalyze any chemical reaction in living and non-living creatures. This catalyst, which aids in increasing the rate of reaction to the desired level under physiological

conditions, is known as "enzymes". It is beneficial in every stage, including industry, medical, laundry, textiles, baking applications, etc., where organic chemical reactions occur. It changes the whole process without changing itself [17]. Schwann extracted the first enzyme from an animal source, pepsin, in 1834 by acid extraction of the animal stomach wall [18]. In laundry industry, enzyme is mainly used to enhance the performance of stain removers and detergents at low temperatures. Its main function is to remove stains from fabric in an environment friendly manner and also performing other functions such as protecting cotton fibers.

According to Vitolo [19], enzymes are made up of a three-dimensional structure composed of a linear chain of amino acids. These amino acids help to find the catalytic activity of enzymes. At high temperature, enzymes lose their structure and catalytic capabilities. The efficient use of enzymes, particularly in industry, is dependent on striking equilibrium between the quantity of enzyme required, operating conditions, and reaction yields [20]. Enzymes are used in laundry detergents to dissolve protein, fat, or starch stains on clothing. Enzymes (proteases) were first introduced in laundry detergents in late 1960s. Nowadays, they are extensively utilized for their novel and varied capabilities [21].

There are six types of enzymes: Oxidoreductases, Transferases, Hydrolyzers, Ligases, Isomerizers, and Lyases. According to Vitolo [19], Novozyme, which produces enzyme based products states that "Hydrolyzers which dissolve protein, fat, and carbohydrate soils, are among the most commonly used detergents and stain remover enzymes. In one of the study, Novozymes [16] compared enzymes and surfactants to remove fabric stains. The study compared four different types of solutions with varying amounts of surfactant and enzyme to 36 different types of common daily stains. The study concluded that replacing enzymes with surfactants can improve stain removal on fabric while remaining eco-friendly and relatively inexpensive. Proteases, Lipases, Amylases, Manganese, Cellulose and Pectin are the most common types of hydrolyzing enzymes used in the textile laundry industry and detergent industry. According to recent research, multi-enzyme systems can replace up to 25% of a laundry detergents surfactant component without sacrificing washing effectiveness [22].

2.1.3.1 Enzyme Action

Enzymes are protein-based biological catalysts. Catalysts are substances that speed up chemical reactions while remaining unchanged themselves. Substrate is the chemical on which enzymes work. An enzyme and its substrate unite to produce an enzyme/substrate complex. In fig.2 when the process is finished, the complex degrades into products and enzymes, with the enzyme remaining unaltered [23].

Figure 2: lock and key model of enzyme

Source: <https://www.alamy.com/stock-photo/lock-and-key-enzyme.html?cutout=1&sortBy=relevant>

The same thing happens with enzyme stain removers and detergents. They convert the complicated stain chain structure into a simple, water-soluble chain. Enzymes increase the rate of reaction 10 times [13]. It helps to balance the reaction between reactant and product. When the reaction begins, the reactant or substrate attains a much higher level of energy, which is referred to as the transition state in fig.3. The energy required in reaching a reactant or substrate in a transition state is known as activation energy. This energy acts as an impediment to the entire reaction. The catalyzed enzyme helps in lowering the activation energy, and the rate of reaction increases rapidly. The rate of catalyzed reaction is the same in both directions because the transition rate is the same in catalyzed reaction [18, 23].

Figure 3: Need for energy in case of unanalyzed and enzyme catalyzed reactions

Source: <https://www.scribd.com/document/210542816/EnzymeKinetics-by-P-C-Misra-Professor-Department-of-Biochemistry-Lucknow-University-Lucknow-226-007>

2.1.3.2 Mechanisms of Enzyme for Removing Stain

Enzymes speed up the action of surfactants in laundry. Microorganisms produce enzyme products during fermentation processes. Proteins, which include enzymes, are easily biodegradable in the ecosystem. Starch and sugar, which are mostly produced by agriculture, are utilised as feedstock in the manufacture of enzymes. When enzymes break up stains, they behave like miniature Pac-Man characters as shown in fig 4. They break down the complex structure of stain into small molecule. Laundry stains can be more easily cleaned since molecules have smaller bits. Each kind of enzyme works best on particular kind of stain in laundry. For example, the lipase enzyme removes fatty and oily stains. Protease, which is the most important enzyme in laundry cleaning, helps remove protein-based stains very easily. The amylase enzyme removes a starch-based stain. The mannanase enzyme removes mannan-based stains like those in ice cream and yoghurt. On cotton fabrics, Cellulases enzymes are capable of removing protruding fiber ends, preventing fading, and preventing the development of "pills" after use and washing Novozymes [2, 13].

As per study done by Nova, it was reported that nine parameters influenced enzyme wash efficacy, which includes detergent composition, enzyme concentration, temperature, pH, water hardness, contact duration, type of dirt, type of wash system, and type of wash procedure.

Figure 4: The function of an amylase enzyme

Source: <https://www.novozymes.com/en/campaigns/towards-100-biological-detergents>

2.1.3.3 Type of laundry enzymes

Proteases, Lipases, Amylases, and Cellulases are the four main categories of detergent enzymes, and each has its own advantages for use in laundry.

Proteases: The enzymes that are widely used in laundry detergents are proteases to remove protein based stains such as grass, eggs, blood, etc. [24]. Proteases are common enzymes found throughout nature [25]. The catalytic enzymes known as proteases or peptidases aid the hydrolysis of peptide bonds. They are present in all living things and also play a crucial role in both physiological and metabolic processes [17, 23]. There are several sources of protease enzymes which exist in plants, animals, and microbes [25]. Otto Röhm, a German scientist, originally developed proteases enzyme in 1913 as an active agent in laundry detergents for the removal of protein

stains. Gerbruder Schnyder created the first commercial protease-containing detergent in 1959. Due to the growing awareness towards environment friendly technologies, proteases, especially alkaline proteases, represent a significant amount of promise for use in the detergent and leather industries [23].

Amylase: An enzyme called amylase is employed to break down the starch-based stain on the cloth. After proteases, amylases are the second most common enzyme used in the detergent business, making up 30% of total sales. The hydrolyses known as "amylases" (EC 3.2.1.1) work on the 1,4-glycosidic linkages of starch as well as other related molecules to produce a wide range of products, including sucrose, maltotriose, and corn flour. Animals, plants, microbes and bacillus species are the main source of amylases. Alpha and beta are the two categories of amylases; they attack the starch molecules in different ways [21]. Half of the enzyme market in the world is dominated by Bacillus species. Bacterial amylases are made using two different fermentation processes: submerged fermentation and solid-state fermentation. The ideal temperature for most bacterial amylase detergents is 20–60 °C, and the ideal pH range for bacterial detergent is 7.0–11.0. Around 30% of the world's detergent industries and 90% of the solid-liquid laundry use amylases, which are produced by the worldwide enzyme industry [26]. The necessity to provide a low-cost medium for increased production and the potential uses of amylase in a variety of sectors including detergents offers great opportunity for increasing amylase manufacturing [27]. Amylases, usually combined with proteases, help detergents clean dishes and fabrics. They are also employed in the sectors of institutional and industrial cleaning [23].

Lipase: In 1856, Claude Bernard discovered the first lipases, which dissolve the insoluble oil droplets and transform them into a soluble product, in the pancreatic fluid of a dead animal [28]. Lipases are present in all living things, including plants, animals or microbes, and the biggest source of the lipase enzyme is microorganisms. Long-chain fatty acid esters of glycerol are broken by hydrolyses known as lipases (EC 3.1.1.3) at the water-oil interface [30]. In a number of processes, such as the conversion of triacylglycerol into diacylglycerols, monoacylglycerols, fatty acids, and glycerol, lipases function as catalysts between the aqueous and lipid phases [31]. Serine hydrolyses which are present in large amounts in lipases and are members of the triacylglycerol ester hydrolyse family [29]. The primary bacteria found in lipase detergent come from acinetobacter, bacillus, burkholderia, streptomyces, rhodococcus, pseudomonas, staphylococcus, aspergillus, cryptococcus, fusarium, talaromyces, and trichosporon [28]. After proteases and amylases, lipases are the third most common industrial enzyme. It was shown that phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride which acts as an obstruction had an unfavorable effect on the activity of most lipase enzymes. Fermentation is a cheap medium for making the lipase enzyme. Submerged fermentation (SMF) produces a large contingent of extracellular enzymes. According to T. Asahii, yeast requires 32 hours of fermentation before producing the lipase enzyme [30]. For microbial detergent lipases, a pH range of 7.0–11.0 is suitable. The introduction of industrial microbial lipases by the detergent industry has been a game-changer for replacing harsh chlorine bleach with lipase and reducing industrial and sewage pollution in fresh water. Thermomyces lanuginosus was used to make the first commercially accessible recombinant lipase, known as lipolase, which was then expressed in Aspergillus oryzae. A. oryzae was used to produce the first commercial lipase that was isolated from trichoderma lanuginosus in 1994. They also manufacture the lipase-containing detergent LipoPrime® [28].

Cellulases: The enzyme known as cellulose breaks down the 1, 4-glucoside linkages in the cellulose chain. In ecology, Endoglucanases (EC 3.2.1.4), Exoglucanases (EC 3.2.1.91), or β -glycosidase are the three main types of cellulases that work together in a coordinated way to completely depolymerize cellulases to glucose (EC 3.2.1.21). They are created by fungi, plants, bacteria, protozoans, or animals and are found all over the natural world [23]. There are many negative effects seen on fabric texture and fabric strength due to the use of chemicals. The demand for the cellulases enzyme has increased rapidly these days due to adverse effects of different chemicals. Detergents employ Endoglucanases and Exoglucanases to improve cleaning, color brilliance, or fabric smoothing [32].

The removal of short fibers and surface fuzziness by the action of celluloses results in a smooth and glossy look, improved color brightness, increased hydrophilicity and moisture absorption. Cellulases usage also aids in softening clothing and removing debris that has become lodged inside the microfibrillar chain [33]. Few companies have also started producing cold-active celluloses. Among them are Novozymes, which creates

Celluzyme and Celluclean; dyadic, which makes Rocksoft Antarctic and Antarctic LTC for use in the production of detergents; and Dupont, which produces Prima fast Gold, HSL Indige, and Prima Green to be used in the textile manufacturing industry [34].

3. Challenges faced by enzymes based stain remover and detergent

According to enzyme technical association [23, 35], Enzyme-based detergents and stain removers are generally considered safe and effective for removing stains and cleaning laundry. However, some potential harmful effects can occur with their use:

Effect on human body: Enzymes in detergents and stain removers can cause skin allergies, respiratory issues, and eye irritation. Caution is advised when using enzyme-based products to minimize the risk of these side effects.

pH levels: Enzymes have an optimal pH range at which they work best. If the pH is too high or too low, the enzymes may become denatured and lose their effectiveness.

Temperature: Enzymes are sensitive to temperature and can become denatured or degraded if exposed to high temperatures. Some enzymes work best at lower temperatures, while others require higher temperatures to activate.

Type of stain: Different enzymes work best on different types of stains. For example, protease enzymes are effective at breaking down protein-based stains like blood or grass, while amylase enzymes are effective at breaking down starch-based stains like food.

Concentration of enzymes: The concentration of enzymes in a detergent or stain remover can affect its effectiveness. Higher concentrations of enzymes can improve the product's ability to break down stains but may also make it more expensive [19, 21].

Overall, enzyme-based detergents and stain removers can have excellent durability, especially when used correctly and with the appropriate concentration of enzymes. However, the durability can vary depending on the specific product and the conditions in which it is used. It is important to use enzyme-based detergents and stain removers in moderation and to follow the instructions carefully to minimize these potential harmful effects. Additionally, it may be recommended to use natural alternatives or eco-friendly products when possible to mitigate the harmful effects to both humans and the environment.

4. Conclusion

Based on current review, it can be concluded that chemical-based detergents and stain removers have a negative environmental impact. These products often contain harsh chemicals that can be harmful to both the environment and human health and can contribute to water pollution, damage aquatic life, and contribute to air pollution. On the other hand, enzyme-based detergents and stain removers have a positive impact on both fabric and the environment. They are also biodegradable and do not accumulate in the environment, making them a more sustainable and eco-friendly option. Studies have shown that enzyme-based products are effective at removing tough stains and are gentle on fabrics, making them a popular choice for consumers. Additionally, the use of these products can reduce the amount of water and energy needed for laundry, further reducing their environmental impact.

Overall, the use of enzyme-based detergents and stain removers is a more environmentally responsible choice compared to traditional chemical-based products.

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